

A Comparative Study on Consumer's Behaviour towards Organized and Unorganized Retailing in Central Chennai

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ABSTRACT

Retailing consists of all activities involved in selling goods and services to consumers for their personal, family, or household use. It covers sales of goods ranging from automobiles to apparel and food products, and services ranging from hair cutting to air travel and computer education retailing is one of the largest sectors in the global economy. In India for a long time the corner grocery store was the only choice available to the consumers with the increasing demand of the customers spurred by changing trends, aspiring needs for variety, the traditional retail gave rise to modern retail format. The traditional food and grocery segment has seen the emergence of supermarkets/grocery chains, convenience stores and hypermarkets.

At present India is rapidly evolving in to an existing and Competitive market place with potential target consumers in both the rich and middle class segments. Manufacturer owned and retail chain stores are springing up in urban area to market consumer's goods in a style similar to

that of mall in more affluent countries. Even though big retail chain like Crossroad, Saga and Shopper's stop are concentrating on the upper segment and selling products at higher prices, some like A.V Birla Retails. More, RPG's Spencer's, Food World and Big Bazaars are tapping the huge middle class population. During the past two years, there has been tremendous amount of Interest in the Indian retail trade from global majors as well as over the years. An attempt is made in this article for now the consumer buying behaviour towards organized and unorganized retail outlets.

Keywords: *Retailing, Organized Retailing, Unorganized Retailing, Consumer Behaviour, Retail Industry Formats*

INTRODUCTION:

Marketing is the science of meeting the needs of a customer by providing valuable products to customers by utilizing the expertise of the organization, at same time, to achieve organizational goals. Classical

marketing is often described in terms of the four “P’s”, which

- Product – what goods or services are offered to customers
- Promotion – how the producer communicates the value of its products
- Price – the value of the exchange between the customer and producer
- Placement – how the product is delivered to the customer.

Marketing has both inbound and outbound activities. Inbound activities largely centre on discovering the needs and wants of the potential customers. The collective group of all potential customers is called a market. Categorizing these needs into groups is called segmentation. Organizing markets into segments allows a producer to more logically decide how to best provide value to that group of potential customers. The analysis of market segment needs; analysis of existing sales and profitability; the descriptions, design and introduction of new products; and the analysis of competitor offerings are also inbound activities that are important but not often seen by the public. Outbound activities include all aspects of informing the market that a product is available, delivering that product, and encouraging the purchase decision. These activities include advertising, promotion, supply chain, sales support, product training, and customer support.

ORGANIZED RETAILING:

Organized traders/retailers, who are licensed for trading activities and registered to pay taxes to the government. Organized retailing comprises mainly of modern retailing with busy shopping malls, multi stored malls and huge complexes that offer a large variety of products in terms of quality, value for money and makes shopping a memorable experience. The retail sector is presently undergoing a transition in India. Previously, customers used to go to kirana Stores to purchases their necessities. This later changed to bigger shops run by one man with a few employees. Here all the work was done manually. Gradually more sophistication seeped into this sector and department stores came into being. Beginning in the mid- 1990s, however, there was an explosion of shopping malls and plazas where customers interacted with professional and not with just one single person – the owner. An important point here is that customers’ requirements are catered to by trained

staff. Today, organized retailing has become an experience characterized by comfort, style and speed. It is something that offers a customer more control, convenience and choice along with an experience. Organized retailing is on continuous increase of its market share from the past. Retailing can be categorized as of different sectors like food and grocery, clothing and textiles, consumer durables, footwear, furniture and furnishing, catering services, jewelry and watches, books, music and gifts, mobile handsets and others.

UNORGANIZED RETAILING:

It consists of unauthorized small shops conventional Kirana shops, general stores, corner shops among various other small retail outlets but remain as the radiating force of Indian retail industry. Unorganized retailing refers to the traditional formats of low cost retailing for example, the local kirana shops, owner manned general stores, paan-bidi shops, convenience store, hand cart and pavement vendors. Traditional or unorganized retailing continuous to be the back bone of the Indian retail industry, with traditional retailing contributing to over 95% of total retail revenues. The prototypical ‘baniya’ outlets or the corner store comprise a key part of Indian retail store formats mostly run as small family business. The unorganized retailing comprises of ‘mom and pop’ stores or ‘kirana’ stores. These are very small shops located near the residential areas, popularly known as kirana shops. The unique marketing preposition of this store is location advantage. These shop owners in order to retain their customer can even go their customer’s house to get orders. Trading hours are flexible and the retailer to consumer ratio is very low due to the presence of several kirana stores in the locality. Credit facility varies from store to store and customer to customer. Customers’ reliability and relation with the shop kipper is enough to avail credit facility. Branding is not a criterion to attract the customers, as customers prefer low-priced products. More than 99% customers are price sensitive and not quality or brand sensitive at the same time they are brand conscious also. Further retailer’s suggestions and recommendation regarding any product or service plays a significant role in the customer’s purchase decision. More than 99% of retailers function in less than 500 Sq. Ft of area. The pricing was done on ad hock basis or by seeing the face of customer. More than 99% customers are price sensitive and not quality or brand sensitive at the same time they are brand conscious also. Traditionally, retailers procure

merchandise from whole seller in bulk and sell in small quantities to the ultimate customer. All the merchandise was purchased as per the test & fancies of the proprietor.

Retail Industry:

Retail is the sale of goods to end users, not for resale, but for use and consumption by the purchaser. The word retail is derived from the French word retailer, meaning to cut a piece off or to break bulk. In simple terms, it implies a first – hand transaction with the customer. Retailing can be defines as the buying and selling of goods and services. It can also be defined as the timely delivery of goods and services demanded by consumers at prices that are competitive and affordable.

Thus retailing can be said to be the interface between the producer and the individual consumer buying for personal consumption. This excludes direct interface between the manufacturers and institutional buyers such as the government and other bulk customers. Retailing is the last link that connects the individual consumers with the manufacturing and distribution chain. A retailer is involved in the act of selling goods to the individual consumer at a margin of profit.

Market Scenario:

The retail market is expected to reach a whopping Rs. 47 lakh crore by 2016-17, as it expands at a compounded annual growth rate of 15 per cent. The retail market, (including organized and unorganized retail), was at Rs. 23 lakh crore in 2011-12. According to the study, organized retail, that comprised just seven per cent of the overall retail market in 2011-12, is expected to grow at a CAGR of 24 per cent and attain 10.2 per cent share of the total retail sector by 2016-17.

In terms of sheer space, the organized retail supply in 2013 was about 4.7 million square feet (square. feet.). This showed a 78 per cent increase over the total mall supply of just 2.5 million sq. ft. in 2012. “Favorable demographics, increasing urbanization, nuclearisation of families, rising affluence amid consumers, growing preference for branded products and higher aspirations are other factors which will drive retail consumption in India,”

Market Dynamics:

In the past few years, Indian Retail sector has seen tremendous growth in the organized segment. Major

domestic players have stepped into the retail arena with long term, ambitious plans to expand their business across verticals, cities and formats. Companies like Tata, Reliance, Adani Enterprise and Bharti have been investing considerably in the booming Indian Retail market. Along with these giant retailers, a number of transnational brands have also entered into the market to set up retail chains in close association with bigger Indian companies.

High consumer spending over the years by the young population (more than 31% of the country is below 14 years) and sharp rise in disposable income are driving the Indian organized retail sector’s growth. Even Tier I & Tier II cities and towns are witnessing a major shift in consumer preferences and lifestyles, the result of which, they have emerged as attractive markets for retailers to expand their presence. The Indian retail sector is highly fragmented and the unorganized sector has around 13 million retail outlets that account for around 95-96% of the total Indian retail industry. However, going forward, the organized sector’s growth potential is expected to increase due to globalization, high economic growth, and improved lifestyle. Although the growth potential in the sector is immense, there are obstacles too, that could slow the pace of growth for new entrants. Rigid regulations, high personnel costs, real estate costs, lack of basic infrastructure, and highly competitive domestic retailer groups are some such challenges.

Retail Industry Formats in India:

Hyper Marts/ Super Markets: Large self – servicing outlets offering products from a variety of categories. Examples like Spencer’s, Big Bazaar.

Mom-and –pop Stores: They are family owned business catering to small sections; they are individually handled retail outlets and have a personal touch.

Departmental Stores: Are general retail merchandisers offering quality products and services. Examples like Ebony, Shopper’s Stop, Westside.

Convenience Stores: Are located in residential areas with slightly higher prices goods due to the convenience offered. Examples like in&Out, Safal, 6ten.

Shopping Malls: The biggest form of retail in India, malls offers customers a mix of all types of products

and services including entertainment and food under a single roof.

E-trailers: Are retailers providing online buying and selling of products and services.

Discount Stores: These are factory outlets that give discount on the MRP. Examples like Subhiksha, Koutons, Nike, and Levis.

Vending: It is a relatively new entry in the retail sector. Here beverages, snacks and other small items can be bought via vending machines.

Category Killers: Small specialty stores that offers a variety of categories. They are known as category killers as they focus on specific categories, such as electronics and sporting goods. This is also known as Multi Brand Outlets or MBO's.

Specialty Stores: are retail chains dealing in specific categories and provide deep assortment. Mumbai's Crossword Book Store and RPG's Music World is a couple of examples.

Trends in Indian retailing:

Within retail, the emerging sectors would be food and grocery, apparel, electronics, e-commerce, fashion and lifestyle. Incorporation of technology in the organized retail segment has been something to reckon with in the past few years. Use of computers for merchandise planning and management, control of inventory costs and supplies and replenishment of goods done electronically, internal store billing, etc. has changed the face of product retailing. Online retail business is the next gen format which has high potential for growth in the near future. After conquering physical stores, retailers are now foraying into the domain of e-retailing. The retail industry is all set to test waters over the online medium, by selling products through websites. Food and grocery stores comprises the largest chunk of the Indian retail market. An emerging trend in this segment is the virtual formats where customer orders are taken online through web portals which are delivered at the door step the very same day or the following day. This trend has been catching up with most of the large sized retail chains that have their websites.

At the seventh Food and Grocery Forum India, the opportunities in food and grocery retail in India are immense, given that it constitutes about 69 per cent of India's total retail market. The Indian retail market, currently estimated at \$490 billion, is project to grow

at a compounded annual growth rate of 6 per cent to reach \$865 billion by 2023. Modern retail with a penetration of only 5% is expected to grow about six times from the current 27 billion USD to 220 billion USD, across all categories and segments.

Organized Retail is emerging as the new phenomenon in India and despite the slump, the market is growing exponentially. As economic growth brings more of India's people into the consuming classes and organized retail lures more and more existing shoppers, by 2015, more than 300 million shoppers are likely to patronize organized retail chains. Consumer markets in emerging market economies like India are growing rapidly owing to robust economic growth. India's modern consumption level is set to double within five years to US\$ 1.5 trillion from the present level of US\$ 750 billion. The growing middle class is an important factor contributing to the growth of retail in India. By 2030, it is estimated that 91 million households will be 'middle class', up from 21 million today. Also by 2030, 570 million people are expected to live in cities, nearly twice the population of the United States today. Thus, with tremendous potential and huge population, India is set for high growth in consumer expenditure. With India's large 'young' population and high domestic consumption, the macro trends for the sector look favorable.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The success of the retail store depends on the purchase made by the consumers in the particular retail stores. This study helps to analyse the Consumer Shopping habits, Perception, Image and Attributes in the retail stores.

Since the Customers play the major role in purchasing the Products in both the Retail Stores So this study helps the Retail Owners to improve their Future Sales by the Suggestions and Recommendations of the Study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the need and importance of "Consumer Behaviour towards Organized and Unorganized retail stores".
- To study the reasons for buying from a particular organized and unorganized retail store.
- To study the type of goods customers prefer to purchase in each format.

- To find out what attributes consumers are looking for in retailing product.
- To provide recommendations to serve customers Quickly, Efficiently and Conveniently.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study emphasis the scope to identify the importance of the organized and unorganized Retail Industry. The major part of the study focused on understanding the Consumer Behaviour and patterns of Retail Customers. The study consists of the comprehensive analysis. Retail formats, present Retail scenario and the factors responsible for the development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ali, Kapoor. & Moorthy, 2013 in their study indicated that consumers Shopping behaviour was influenced by their income and educational level while gender and age had no significant impact on their behaviour.

Chakra borty et al 2017 Rural sector in India is undergoing a rapid change. Rural markets consisted major part of unorganized retails stores. But with the changing global scenario, Indian rural market is also changing and has become a new destination of retailing. Study attempts to discuss the recent Indian rural demography and the present day situation of retailing in India, challenges faced by organized and unorganized retailing in rural area. Primary data has been collected from rural villages and described their changing want, value, desire and feelings on retail industry.

Gupta, 2014 concluded in her study that store attributes like convenient operating hours and accessibility were the factors which lead to customer loyalty and not store appearance. Similarly,

Joseph, Soundararajan, Gupta, & Sahu, 2012 concluded that unorganized retailers in the locality of organized retailers were adversely affected in terms of their volume of business and

Kearney, 2012 found that traditional markets are transforming themselves in new formats such as departmental stores, hypermarkets, supermarkets and specialty stores.

Munjal, Kumar, & Narwal, 2013 through their research concluded that the kirana shops“ being

affected by malls is only a myth. He further concluded that in spite of the available opportunities

Nair & Nair, 2016 in their study revealed that the perception of Service quality was influenced by various natures among various customers and some of the general factors like personal interaction, physical aspects on which customer perception remained constant and common. But Singh & Agarwal, (2016) revealed that customer’s Preferences for grocery shopping were gradually shifting from local kirana stores to organized convenience stores. Brand choice and credit card facilities were the main determinants which influenced preferences from kirana to organized retail. Payment through credit cards increased purchases from organized retail store.

Pandey et al 2017 A study was conducted to know the preference of consumers in Jalandhar towards organized retail sector. Study was conducted to assess the important factors influencing the consumers’ buying decision towards organized retail stores in Jalandhar, using the direct survey method Preferred by customers because of various reasons viz. convenient location, home delivery, personal relations with shopkeeper, giving products on credit, payment in instalments. Product attributes like freshness of the product and availability of products range according to the pocket were major determinant of loyalty. It was also evident that even today Kiranas are Profit. According to him with the emergence of organized outlets consumers gained through the availability of better quality products, lower prices, one-stop shopping, choice of additional brands and products, family shopping, and fresh stocks. According to report of ICRIER“organized and unorganized retail not only coexist but also grow substantially. “The reason behind that the retail sector is gradually growing on an overall basis hence the benefit of this growth goes to both the sectors.

Ramanathan&Hari 2013 observed from their study that due to the recent changes in the demographic system of consumers, and the awareness of quality conscious consumption, consumers preferred to buy different products both from the organized and unorganized retailers.

Rathore et al 2015. Similar study was conducted for consumer’s preference in the area of Udaipur. Chi square and ANOVA test were used to interpret the result and to find the suggestions. The major purpose

was to find the responses of the consumers towards the organized and unorganized retailing.

Singh et al 2016 the retailing sector has undergone significant transformation in the past 10 years. Traditionally, retail sector had a large number of small-unorganized retailers. However, in the past decade new concept of organized retailing developed. Many foreign formats have also entered India through different routes such as test marketing, franchising.

Sinha & Banerjee, 2012 in their study concluded that store convenience and customer services positively influenced consumers store selection.

Sivaraman.P, 2013 from his study concluded that the impact of organized retailers was clearly visible on the business of unorganized retailers in terms of sales, profit and employment. Due to their financial infirmity these small retailer continuously struggled to introduce changes in their existing retail practices. Some kind of intervention was required for their future existence.

Solagaard & Hansen, 2012 identified several store attributes that were considered important for the consumer's evaluation of stores. These attributes were merchandise, assortment, merchandise quality, personnel, store layout, accessibility, cleanliness and atmosphere.

Somasekhar G et al 2016 Organized retail sector includes various numbers of sub-sectors in it like jewellery, apparels, food etc. Initially food retailing was a family owned business (they come under unorganized retail store type) but later it has gone through a sea change. Now, the big corporate houses are in the business of food retailing which provides many frill services with quality products. Study was attempted to find the consumers' preference for organized food retailing and unorganized food retailing. The study focuses on the retail attributes which are considered while selecting a retail shop by the consumers.

Somasekhar G et al 2016 the study conducted by considering 342 shoppers who shop at both the outlets. The study reveals that Quality, one point shopping for all your needs and price (value for money) as a reasons to visit and face-inconvenient location as the major problem in visiting organized retail store in Chittor district.

Srivastava et al 2015. Traditionally shopping of jewelry was not very fascinating and exciting. The significance of jewelry has drawn attention of big companies like Titan Industries Ltd., Gitanjali Jewels, PC Jewelers, and Kaylan Jewelers etc. With the entry of big corporate, the traditional retailers of gold jewelry are facing challenges with regard to quality, design, availability, warranty, brand image, service and store environment and display as well. Study was conducted on which stores consumers prefer and why. Similarly studies in other sectors were also conducted to know the preference of consumers on sub sector in organized retail.

Srivastava, 2014 in his study showed that the overall customers' perception across urban and suburban was not varied. The customers were ready to pay higher prices for branded goods across the urban and suburban areas. They gave priority to purchase grocery from nearby shops while for purchasing of apparel they liked to travel some distance. The outcomes of the study showed that the exposure of marketing strategy through electronic and print media made the customers more choosy and knowledgeable. To the organized retail to grow in India these kirana shops also were benefited from this growing economy.

Tamar et al 2015 There are different categories of customers which need to be considered. The number of working in India is increasing day by day and hence their attitude towards organized cannot be ignored which prompted to study their attitude towards organized retailing in India. Exploratory research was conducted; survey on 150 working women of Agra, Gwalior and National Capital Region was undertaken. The survey was conducted at the various organized retail outlets. It was found that organized retailers should work up on the delivery channels to increase the frequency of visit of working women.

Tamar et al 2016. Unfortunately, Indian organized retailers being new in the organized retailing are less aware about the customer behavior and factors, which influence Customer Preference of organized retailing. Study was conducted to know how the factors affecting organized retailing differentiate between favorable and unfavorable attitude towards organized retailing. Discriminate analysis is done to find out which factor (store brand image, quality of merchandise, discount and special offer, merchandise

assortment, shopping convenience, and physical facilities) are relatively better in discriminating between two groups (favorable attitude-unfavorable attitude). Also, the pace of expansion of these organized stores has started to touch the tier II cities, besides metros and mini-metros.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design followed for the study is descriptive type of research. In this study Stratified random sampling technique is used for data collection among the respondents. Total sample size for this research study is 200. The primary instrument used in the study is “Questionnaire ”. Secondary data is obtained from company profile, internet, various other documents, scope need and other reports of the company. Statistical tools used for this study i.e. Percentage Analysis, Chi square Test, and Correlation Analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis and interpretation is an important part of any kind of inter data analysis the researcher can begin to identify relationship between various data that will help to understand more about the respondents and guide towards better decisions. The tools for this study are chi square, correlation and ANOVA and percentage analysis.

CORRELATION IN ORGANIZED RETAIL STORES:

Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no relationship between the Income of the respondents and the respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Organized Retailing.

Alternative hypothesis (H₁): There is a relationship between the Income of the respondents and the respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Organized Retailing.

TABLE NO: 1 Pearson’s Correlation Table Showing difference between the Income of the Respondents and Respondents towards the Variety of the Product

a) Organized Retailing

Pearson Correlations			
		Income of the respondents in the family purchased in organized retail stores	Respondents opinion towards the variety of the product available in the Particular shop of organized retail stores
Income of the respondents in the family purchased in organized retail stores	Pearson Correlation	1	-.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.776
	N	120	120
Respondents opinion towards the variety of the product available in the Particular shop of organized retail stores	Pearson Correlation	-.026	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.776	
	N	120	120

RESULT: Since P value is more than the 0.05 accept H_0 . Correlation Point is (-0.26) it lies between the Negative values of -1. So there is no relationship between the Income of the respondents and the respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Organized Retailing.

CORRELATION IN UNORGANIZED RETAIL STORES:

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no relationship between the Income of the respondents and the

TABLE NO: 1 b) Unorganized Retailing

Pearson's Correlations			
		Income of the respondents in the family purchased in unorganized retail stores	Respondents opinion towards the variety of the product available in the Particular shop of unorganized retail stores
Income of the respondents in the family purchased in unorganized retail stores	Pearson Correlation	1	-.501**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	80	80
Respondents opinion towards the variety of the product available in the Particular shop of unorganized retail stores	Pearson Correlation	-.501**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	80	80

RESULT:

Since P value is lesser than the 0.05 Reject H_0 . Correlation Point (-0.501) it lies between the Negative values of -1. So there is a relationship between the Income of the respondents and the respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Unorganized Retailing.

CHI-SQUARE TEST IN ORGANIZED RETAIL STORES:

respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Unorganized Retailing.

Alternative hypothesis (H_1): There is a relationship between the Income of the respondents and the respondents Opinion towards the Variety of the Product in Unorganized Retailing.

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between Age group of the respondents purchased in organized retail stores and the Respondents opinion on purchase of Food Items in the organized retail stores.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference between Age group of the respondents purchased in organized retail stores and the Respondents opinion on purchase of Food Items in the organized retail stores.

Age group of the respondents purchased in organized retail stores*Respondents opinion on purchase of food items in the organized retail stores.

TABLE NO: 2 Table Showing the Chi-square Analysis between the Age Group and Purchase of Food Items

a).Organized Retailing

Age group of the respondents in organized retail stores		Respondents opinion on purchase of Food ITEMS in the organized retail stores					Total
		HIGHLY DIS SATISFIED	DIS SATISFIED	NEUTRAL	SATIS FIED	HIGHLY SATISFIED	
	Less than 20 years	0	0	0	0	8	8
	20-30 years	3	4	3	8	27	45
	30-40 years	4	3	3	5	18	33
	40-50 years	4	2	4	7	11	28
	Above 50 years	0	1	1	0	4	6
Total		11	10	11	20	68	120

TABLE NO: 2 Table Showing Chi Square Test

Organized Retailing

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.110 ^a	16	.590
Likelihood Ratio	18.264	16	.309
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.742	1	.053
N of Valid Cases	120		
a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50.			

RESULT:

Since calculated value is greater than the tabulated value reject Ho. So there is a significant difference between the age group of the respondent's purchased in organized retail stores and the respondent's opinion on purchase of food items in the organized retail stores.

CHI-SQUARE TEST IN UNORGANIZED RETAIL STORES:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between Age group of the respondents purchased in unorganized retail stores and the Respondents opinion on purchase of Food Items in the organized retail stores.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is a significant difference between Age group of the respondents purchased in unorganized retail stores and the Respondents opinion on purchase of Food Items in the organized retail stores.

Age group of the respondents purchased in unorganized retail stores*Respondents opinion on purchase of food items in the unorganized retail stores.

TABLE NO: 2(b) Unorganized Retailing

Age group of the respondents in unorganized retail stores	Respondents opinion on purchase of Food ITEMS in the unorganized retail stores					Total
	HIGHLY DISSATISFIED	DISSATISFIED	NEUTRAL	SATISFIED	HIGHLY SATISFIED	
Less than 20 years	0	0	1	2	0	3
20-30 years	6	9	10	3	3	31
30-40 years	8	6	2	5	2	23
40-50 years	6	3	3	4	3	19
Above 50 years	1	2	1	0	0	4
Total	21	20	17	14	8	80

TABLE NO: 2(b) Unorganized Retailing

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.455 ^a	16	.422
Likelihood Ratio	17.830	16	.334
Linear-by-Linear Association	.608	1	.436
N of Valid Cases	80		

a. 19 cells (76.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

RESULT:

Since calculated value is greater than the tabulated value reject Ho. So there is a significant difference between the age group of the respondent’s purchased in unorganized retail stores and the respondent’s opinion on purchase of food items in the unorganized retail stores.

CONCLUSION

The concept of retail is comparatively very old in Indian context. Before anybody knew about what retail is, we had kirana stores, medical stores and lot many other stores working surprisingly well all over the country. Recently with the entrance of big players like Wal-Mart or Reliance, people are getting idea of the traditional stores going to be vanished. But just to remind us, we should never forget how deep rooted is this old concept. The very modern organized stores have taken the idea of retailing nowhere else than from these old shops.

The growth in the Indian organized retail market is mainly due to the change in the consumer’s perception. This change has come in the consumer due to increased income, changing lifestyles, and patterns of demography which are favourable. Now the consumer wants to shop at a place where he can get food, entertainment, and shopping all less than one roof. This has given Indian organized retail market a major boost. Thus, in India it is quite sceptical that the organized retail will be ever able to overcome the unorganized retail completely. The values, cultures and beliefs of the customers prompt them to go the same retail shop where they can get the product

required, at low price and with least waiting time for billing. No matter how lucrative is this sector and how bright is the market; the organized sector in retailing has to go a long way to understand the customer requirement and government make available credit at reasonable rates and also encourage setting up of modern large cash-and-carry outlets, which could supply not only to kirana stores but also to licensed hawkers at wholesale rates.

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